

Photolysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ at 254 and 313 nm in Ethylene Glycol-Water, Glycerol-Water and Acetonitrile-Water Mixed Solvent Systems

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Photolysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ by uv radiations in aquo-organic solvent systems of various compositions reveals that the efficiency of the intramolecular photoredox reaction, as manifested in the quantum yield of Co^{2+} , varies in a complex way and no single factor appears capable of explaining all the features of the photolytic behaviour of the complex. The present work tries to explain the variation of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ with composition in mixed solvent systems like ethylene glycol-water, glycerol-water and acetonitrile-water in terms of dielectric constant, viscosity, critical solvation and solvent structure effects. The effect of pH variation on $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ has also been investigated.

Charge-transfer excitation of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ causes an intramolecular redox reaction in which an electron is transferred from an orbital centered on the bromine ligand to an orbital centered on the cobalt metal. The process may be described by the following scheme¹ :

Δ is the amount of light energy absorbed in excess of that required for homolytic dissociation. The sequence of events which lead to the formation of Co^{2+} ions are as follows : (i) excitation, (ii) photophysical processes for the initial CTTM excited state, (iii) fragmentation of the reactive CTTM excited state to form solvent trapped species, (iv) separation of these radical species in the bulk and (v) formation of products.

The shape of the excited state potential energy

surface and the binding energy of the CTTM excited state are to a significant extent functions of the solvent environment². A change in solvation energy would change the energetics of the excited state dissociation and may give rise to activation barrier for radical recombination. The polarity of the solvent plays a dominant role in determining the overall efficiency of the photoredox reaction because the charge of the substrate gets diffused in the excited state. From this simple consideration the quantum yield of Co^{2+} is expected to increase in a less polar solvent since the excited state is less polar compared to the ground state. In some cases, the polarity factor may affect the values of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in a complicated manner as the smaller dipole moment of the excited state would involve large adjustments of environment and during that period many photophysical processes can occur affecting the quantum yield of Co^{2+} in diverse ways. The efficiency of photoinduced intramolecular redox reaction of cobalt(III) complexes also depends on the viscosity or more appropriately on the microscopic viscosity in the immediate neighbourhood of the substrate. The redox decomposition of the complex competes

with cage recombination of the radical pair generated by the primary homolytic bond splitting. The diffusion apart of the radical pair is favoured in a medium of low viscosity.

Results and Discussion

Ethylene glycol-water and glycerol-water : The results presented in Table 1 indicate that the quantum yield of Co^{2+} ($\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$) varies in a complex way with the solvent composition. The incorporation of ethylene glycol or glycerol in water, initially, increases the quantum yields of Co^{2+} but beyond a certain point $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ decreases as the weight percentage of ethylene glycol/glycerol increases. The results provide an evidence of the fact that short range ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions lead to immediate reactive environments which significantly differ in composition from the bulk medium. In 10% ethylene glycol or 12% glycerol, the complex ions are preferentially solvated by water and consequently, the microscopic viscosity of pure water. The increase in the values of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in 10% ethylene glycol or 12% glycerol, compared to the same quantity in pure water is due to the stabilisation of the initial CTTM excited state in less polar environments. The charge transfer transition energy (Z -value) obtained from *N*-methylpyridinium iodide is a measure of the polarity of the mixed solvent systems³ but in the present case the values of dielectric constants have been used as a rough index of polarity owing to non-availability of relevant data (Z -values). In relatively concentrated solutions of ethylene glycol or glycerol, strongly H-bonded organic molecules also enter into the solvation sphere of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ resulting in a sharp increase in the microscopic viscosity although it may not be quite equal to the bulk viscosity of the medium. This leads to a situation which apparently favours the cage recombination of the radical pair generated by the primary homolytic bond splitting. As before, the polarity factor has a positive effect on the efficiency of the intramolecular photoredox process. Of these two contrasting factors, the first one predominates over the second and this explains why $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ decreases as the weight percentage of ethylene glycol or glycerol increases in relatively concentrated solutions.

TABLE 1—QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN ETHYLENE GLYCOL-WATER AND GLYCEROL-WATER MIXED SOLVENT SYSTEMS

[Complex] = 2×10^{-3} M, Time of irradiation = 2 min, Temp = $35 \pm 1^\circ$, pH = 4.63

Wt % of ethylene glycol/glycerol*	Solvent viscosity (bulk) cp	Dielectric constant	Excitation wavelength nm	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
Ethylene glycol-Water				
0	1 002	78.7	254 313	0.33 0.24
10	1 276	75.6	254 313	0.36 0.27
28	2 047	70.4	254 313	0.34 0.25
Glycerol - Water				
52	3 981	62.4	254 313	0.25 0.21
0	1 002	78.7	254 313	0.33 0.24
12	1 365	75	254 313	0.38 0.26
24	1 988	71.7	254 313	0.29 0.22
56	6 666	61.6	254 313	0.25 0.20

*Water used in aquo-organic solvent systems is essentially acetic acid-acetate buffer

Viscosity data at 20° were obtained from Ref. 8 Dielectric constant data at 25° were obtained from Ref. 9

Acetonitrile-water : The results presented in Table 2 reveal the following : (i) $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ increases as the weight percentage of CH_3CN increases, over the entire range of composition and (ii) the increase in $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ from 97.5 to 100% acetonitrile is much more dramatic. These results agree with those of Langford and Lindsay obtained for 254 nm photolysis of the same complex⁴. The initial increase in $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ with the incorporation of acetonitrile in water is due to the preferential solvation of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ by CH_3CN and it is perhaps best regarded as a rejection of CH_3CN by the water structure rather than any ion-solvent interaction. The fractionation of CH_3CN from $\text{CH}_3\text{CN-H}_2\text{O}$ into the solvation sphere of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ lowers the microscopic viscosity and polarity in the neighbourhood of the complex ions and as a consequence, the quantum yield of Co^{2+} increases.

The bulk viscosity and bulk dielectric constant of 97.5% CH_3CN are almost equal to those of 100% CH_3CN but in spite of this, $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ increases dramati-

cally. This apparently unexpected result led Langford and Lindsay to formulate a new hypothesis for the origin of the solvent effect. This model proposes that the role of water is the specific promotion of a quenching process leading to an unreactive state called X :

Their proposition seems to be not very convincing because comparison on the basis of bulk viscosity and bulk dielectric constant is confusing if the reactant environments differ in composition from the bulk medium. There is reason to believe that the marked increase in $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in going from 97.5 to 100% acetonitrile is due to a combination of critical solvation and solvent structure effects as they can bring about a vast change in the microscopic viscosity and microscopic dielectric constant of the microenvironment of the reactive species.

TABLE 2—QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN ACETONITRILE-WATER MIXED SOLVENT SYSTEMS

[Complex] = 2×10^{-3} M, Time of irradiation = 2 min, = $35 \pm 1^\circ$, Excitation wavelength = 313 nm

Wt. % of acetonitrile	Solvent viscosity (bulk) cp	Dielectric constant	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
0	0.890	78.7	0.22
16.5	0.859	68.0	0.25
34.5	0.819	58.1	0.27
54	0.595	48.3	0.31
76	0.430	41.5	0.34
97.5	0.341	36.5	0.36
100	0.340	36.0	0.68

The viscosity and dielectric constant data at 25° were obtained from Ref. 10.

Effect of pH : The results compiled in Table 3 reveal that the quantum yield of Co^{2+} increases with the increase of pH in aqueous solution. The excited state formed on excitation may undergo internal conversion to a second excited state possibly through a loss of proton which amounts to chemical stabilisation of the second state :

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF pH VARIATION ON THE QUANTUM YIELD OF Co^{2+} IN AQUEOUS MEDIA

Medium	Excitation wavelength nm	[Complex] mol dm^{-3}	Time of irradiation min	pH	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
Acetic acid-acetate buffer	254	2×10^{-3}	2	4.63	0.33
				4.10	0.32
				3.72	0.31
	313	5×10^{-3}	2	4.63	0.24
				4.10	0.22
				3.72	0.21

This is an interconversion process coupled with rapid proton transfer to solvent. Thus the initially populated $\text{Br}^- \rightarrow \text{Co}^{(+3)}$ charge-transfer excited state is transformed to $\text{H}_2\text{N}^- \rightarrow \text{Co}^{(+3)}$ charge-transfer excited state. The latter state can not be populated by direct absorption of radiation because it differs stoichiometrically from the ground state. The metastable excited state has comparatively long life. The above equilibrium shifts to the left as pH of the medium decreases and Co^{2+} ions are formed from the less active state, and this is the reason for the decreased quantum yield of Co^{2+} in a medium of lower pH.

Experimental

The complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$ was prepared according to the published procedure⁵. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}](\text{NO}_3)_2$ was synthesised⁴ by treating $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$ with AgNO_3 . In acetonitrile-water mixed solvent systems, two salts of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ had to be used in order to overcome solubility problems. These were the nitrate and the tetraphenylborate salt. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}](\text{BPh}_4)_2$ was prepared by addition of NaBPh_4 to an aqueous solution of the bromide salt.

A low pressure mercury vapour lamp (T/M5/594-110 W) was employed for generating radiation of wavelength 254 nm. For 313 nm irradiation, a medium pressure mercury vapour lamp (H_4 lamp) was used as the source. A solution of potassium chromate was used as a filter for isolating 313 nm radiation from the light of the medium pressure lamp. The intensity of the light was measured by

ferrioxalate actinometry⁶. Solutions of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$, $(2-5) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, were irradiated for 2 min. The Co^{2+} formed was estimated by Kitson's method⁷. The temperature of the solutions were all along maintained at $35 \pm 1^\circ$ by circulating water and using a thermostatic control device. The compositions of the aquo-organic solvent systems were systematically varied so as to study the effects of the reaction medium on the quantum yield of Co^{2+} . The reported values of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ are averages of at least three independent runs.

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